

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY OF PERSONALITY IN SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

Zulayho Saminjonova

Student of Applied Psychology at Fergana State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7306627>

Annotation: In this scientific article, the individuality in social psychology in the study of personality, the impact of existing views in society, in addition to interpersonal relations, on the process of personality formation is discussed.

Key words: Personality concept, personality study, social psychology, sociopsychological approaches, socialization process.

The owner-subject and object of both the communication process and group processes in the social environment is, in fact, an individual. That is why social psychology also studies the problem of the individual, examining him from the point of view of being a participant and an active implementer of those various social processes. Because the personality problem is studied in almost many fields of psychology. For example: general psychology, pedagogical psychology, experimental psychology, differential psychology, legal psychology, etc. But each field studies the personality in terms of its own topics and tasks. For example If general psychology considers a person to be a product of psychological activity, the owner of separate mental processes, sociology considers a person to be an object of social relations.

The peculiarity of the socio-psychological approach to the study of personality is that a person is considered as the result of various forms of interaction with different groups. That is, social psychology, first of all, what is the behavior of a person who is considered a member of a group learns how the influence of the individual in the system of communication is reflected in his consciousness. The way in which the influence of the group on the psychology of the individual occurs is inextricably linked with the problem of socialization in social psychology. How secrets are directly manifested in personal behavior is related to social problems.

The formation of a person's psychology is also influenced by the relations of certain social groups to which he belongs. , affects people, their personal views and social institutions regarding their personal qualities. While living in a certain social environment, a person has a special place there, a reputation will have a role.

The place of each of us in society, when and under what conditions it appeared, the process of psychological mechanisms of joining society is called socialization or socialization in psychology. The term socialization was first applied to people by the American sociologist F.G. Giddings. In his book, Theory of Socialization, he expresses the opinion that "Socialization is the development of individual nature or character, preparation of a person for social life".

In simple words, socialization is the process of every person joining the society, accepting its norms, requirements and influence, showing it in every action and behavior, being able to teach others his social experience.

In modern psychology, two synonyms of the term socialization are widely used: that is, these are the process of "personality formation" and "education". It is also expressed through concepts such as "using them in the process of social communication".

Socialization is the process by which we live in a society and assimilate the social experiences that exist in this society. This process consists of three stages:

Individual social experience

accept, absorb;

use in the process of his life, activity, relationship;

it is the process of being able to transmit it to others, to exert its influence.

Socialization is a two-way process, on the one hand, it is the process of an individual entering the society and mastering its skills, and on the other hand, it is the establishment of social relations through human activity and active participation in society.

Scientists who introduced the idea of socialization into the field of psychology and introduced this problem as a problem for the development of social psychological knowledge paid great attention to two aspects of socialization.

The first part of the process of socialization - the acquisition of social skills - is a description of society that affects a person, and the second part - human activity - the influence of a person on society through his activities. In this, the position of human activity is any influence on social relations. the secret is explained by making a certain decision and then developing a certain strategy of action to carry out this decision.

The socialization of a person appears in the process of his objective need for knowledge. However, with this, the manifestation of another objective need-identity is also formed in the person. as a result, his individualization takes place. Socially important characteristics of a person that belong only to him are manifested in an individual way, and his social behavior has unrepeatable aspects.

In short, a socio-psychological approach to a person is to understand him as a member of certain groups, a concrete person who enters into communication with people similar to him in concrete conditions.

References:

1. Ismailova N. Abdullayeva D. Social psychology. 2013. Short psychological dictionary.
2. Ahrorov V.Y. Social psychology. Samarkand-2020.
3. Ghaziyev E.G. Transactional psychology.

